

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	08	16	Fort-de-France	N	14	39.632	E	-061	14.957
End	2021	09	08	Macapa	N	00	24.009	E	-050	29.315

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAIGN OBJECTIVES

While rivers are an important source of pollutants from land into the Ocean, their plumes also transport large amounts of nutrients that fuel primary production in the coastal waters and open ocean, especially in oligotrophic basins. On the western side of the South Atlantic the two main river inputs are the ones from the Amazon River and the Rio de la Plata, whose plumes are regulated by the local western boundary currents. One of our objectives was to characterise the river input to the ocean and subsequent dilution processes, including the metabolic responses to the fertilization (co-limitations). An important objective of this first campaign in the Atlantic was also to test new sampling strategies, equipment, and protocols.

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin HERTAU
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Nicolas BIN
3	CREW - Mecano	Loïc CAUDAN
4	CREW - Deck	Alain PRIEUR
5	CREW - Deck	François AURAT
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie BIN
7	CREW - Media	Julie NEDELEC-ANDRALE
8	GUEST - Artist	Leslie MOQUIN
9	GUEST - Observer	
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Josep ERTA
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Léa OLIVIER
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Douglas COUET
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Paula HUBER
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Andrea FREIRE
15	SCIENCE - F – acting Chief Scientist	Stéphane PESANT

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

The campaign was conducted in international waters (stations 035 and 036), and in the Exclusive Economic Zones of French Guyana (stations 037 and 038) and Brazil (stations 039 and 040). The study area is characterised by a plume of fresh water originating from the Amazon River and a train of anticyclonic eddies originating from the North Brazilian Current (NBC).

The sampling strategy consisted in sampling (station 035) the north west extension of the Amazon plume in the open ocean, (station 036) a cyclonic eddy outside the footprint of the Amazon plume, (station 037) an anticyclonic eddy originating from the NBC and influenced by low-salinity surface waters from the Amazon plume, (stations 038 & 039) the Amazon plume at the shelf-break and on the shelf, and (station 040) the Amazon River, downstream of Macapa. Protocols were also in place to collect Sargassum and preserve samples for imaging and genetic analysis.

Depending on the scientific objectives and the environmental features present at the different stations, the sampling strategy targeted the surface, epipelagic and/or mesopelagic layers. Five ASP drifters and 40 SPOT drifters were available to track water masses. Additionally, the sampling strategy resolved temporal cycles. Station 039 was sampled during day and night, and station 040 was sampled during Ebb and Flood tides.

Figure 1. Map of Sea Surface Height in the study area on 26.08.2021, with the location of sampling stations

Figure 2. Map of Sea Surface Salinity in the study area on 19.08.2021, with the location of sampling stations

Figure 3. Map of Sea Surface Chlorophyll a in the study area on 22.08.2021, with the location of sampling stations

Figure 4. Tracks of surface drifters released in the study area by SV Tara and RV Anthéa , with measured salinity

Figure 5. Track of SV Tara in the study area, showing underway measurements of surface temperature, salinity and pCO2.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

The scientific objectives were met by sampling key features of the study area, and deploying drifters as a basis to assess/reconstruct the connectivity between the different stations. All sampling equipment and laboratory setups were tested under a wide range of sampling strategies, including long stations where the surface (2 m), epipelagic (30, 70, 120 m) and mesopelagic (400 and 800 m) layers were sampled over a period of 48 hours, short stations where three depths in the epipelagic layer were sampled over a period of 12h, a coastal station where the epipelagic layer was sampled during day and night, and a river station where the epipelagic layer was sampled during ebb and flood tidal periods. All protocols were tested with the exception of dissolved gas (DGAS) and 3D electron microscopy (3DEM5 and 3DEM20). Sargassum was collected successfully at five locations in international waters and was not encountered after station 036.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

Provide an overview of sampling activities on every day of the Campaign, indicating the number of deployments done for each type of event.

Station ###	Date, start YYYY-MM-DD	Latitude, start N dd.dddddd	Longitude, start E ddd.dddddd	UDW - Aerosols	UDW - Biogeochemistry	BGC – CAST – 0-1000	SML	SRF – PUMP	SRF – NET – WPII 20	SRF – NET – WPII 200	SRF – NET – Manta 330	EPI – CAST – 0-200	EPI – NET – WPII 20	EPI – NET – WPII 200	EPI – Régent 680	MESO – CAST – 0-1000	CAST – Trace Metals	VMP – Profile	TIA – Towed Array	Drifters	SARGASSUM	
000	2021-08-17	N 14° 39.632	E -61° 14.957	1	1																	1
000	2021-08-19	N 14° 08.189	E -59° 20.312	1	1																	1
000	2021-08-22	N 16° 22.785	E -57° 31.137	1	1															1		
000	2021-08-22	N 15° 23.452	E -56° 27.383	1	1															1		
000	2021-08-23	N 13° 32.624	E -54° 43.963	1	1																	1
035	2021-08-24	N 12° 32.165	E -57° 57.527	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			5	
000	2021-08-27	N 10° 45.040	E -51° 05.385	1	1																	2
036a	2021-08-28	N 10° 28.216	E -50° 05.219	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1			3	
036b	2021-08-29	N 10° 05.148	E -50° 03.274	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1			3	
036c	2021-08-30	N 09° 41.480	E -49° 30.646	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1			3	
000	2021-08-22	N 09° 24.826	E -49° 38.504	1	1															1	3x2	
037	2021-09-01	N 70° 01.723	E -50° 12.240	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1			3	
000	2021-08-22	N 06° 52.573	E -50° 22.162	1	1															1	2x4	
038a	2021-09-02	N 05° 40.860	E -50° 52.140	1		1										1		1				
038b	2021-09-03	N 05° 16.774	E -51° 13.008	1				1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						3	
039	2021-09-05	N 03° 00.559	E -49° 33.515	1				1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						3	
040	2021-09-07	N 00° 24.0274	E -50° 29.3031	1				1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						3	

Station 35 12 30.11 N 054 05.67 W Aug 25 2021 14:05:13, dCastR011CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 35 12 30.11 N 054 05.67 W Aug 25 2021 14:05:13, dCastR011CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 36a 10 26.99 N 050 07.79 W Aug 28 2021 17:39:28 , dCastR017CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 36a 10 26.99 N 050 07.79 W Aug 28 2021 17:39:28 , dCastR017CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 36b 10 05.08 N 050 02.96 W Aug 29 2021 17:53:47, dCastR022CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 36b 10 05.08 N 050 02.96 W Aug 29 2021 17:53:47, dCastR022CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 36c 09 39.89 N 049 31.88 W Aug 30 2021 18:09:07, dCastR027CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 36c 09 39.89 N 049 31.88 W Aug 30 2021 18:09:07, dCastR027CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 37 07 00.09 N 050 14.42 W Sep 01 2021 13:31:54, dCastR030CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 37 07 00.09 N 050 14.42 W Sep 01 2021 13:31:54, dCastR030CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 38 05 42.98 N 050 53.22 W Sep 02 2021 17:34:13, dCastR035CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 38 05 42.98 N 050 53.22 W Sep 02 2021 17:34:13, dCastR035CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 39 day 02 58.46 N 049 30.50 W Sep 05 2021 20:08:16, dCastR048CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 39 day 02 58.46 N 049 30.50 W Sep 05 2021 20:08:16, dCastR048CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 39night 02 59.32 N 049 31.37 W Sep 06 2021 01:24:09, dCastR050CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 39night 02 59.32 N 049 31.37 W Sep 02 2021 01:24:09, dCastR050CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 40 EBB 00 24.06 N 050 29.29 W Sep 07 2021 11:34:03, dCastR051CSFCLDB.cnv

Station 40 EBB 00 24.06 N 050 29.29 W Sep 07 2021 11:34:03, dCastR051CSFCLDB.cnv

Station 40 FLOOD 23.97 N 050 29.34 W Sep 07 2021 18:50:46, dCastR052CSFACLDB.cnv

Station 40 FLOOD 23.97 N 050 29.34 W Sep 07 2021 18:50:46, dCastR052CSFACLDB.cnv

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

	Storage T°C	RT+10	RT+10	RT+10	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	LN-80	LN-80	LN-80
	Box size	B-Box	G-box	XXL	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	Dewar #1	Dewar #2	Dewar #3
Protocol	Container type												
DGAS	ExeV-12mL						0						
DIC13	200-mL-Bottle		75										
DICTA	500-mL-bottle		43										
DO18	AmberV-40mL			73									
NUT-1	20mLCryoV						78						
SAL	125-mL Bottle			50									
DINO	60-mL-Bottle						28						
MTE	60-mL-Bottle			26									
HG-M	125-mL Bottle			30									
MB320	4-mL-Vial							42					
MB023	4-mL-Vial							42					
MB<02	50-mL-falcon								42				
eDNA	sterivex								43				
NP550	20-mL-vial								33				
NP045	4-mL-Vial							33					
HG	Zip-lock	33											
PM	Zip-lock	42											
S320	5-mL-cryotube										54		
S023	5-mL-cryotube										50		
S<02	5-mL-cryotube							47					
P320	5-mL-cryotube										33		
P023	5-mL-cryotube										33		
HP	2-mL-cryotube											95	
SG	5-mL-cryotube										108		
FC	2-mL-cryotube												137
HC	2-mL-cryotube											144	
SEM	petri-slide	36											
FM20	50-mL-falcon				28								
E20	15-mL-falcon								14				
S20	5-mL-cryotube										14		
S20-L	5-mL-falcon							14					

PM-HG20	Zip-lock	14											
MB20	4-mL-Vial						14						
CP50	petri-slide	14											
SCP50	petri-slide	6											
F200	250-mL-bottle		19										
E200	15-mL-falcon							19					
S200	5-mL-cryotube									19			
S200-L	5-mL-falcon						19						
PM-HG200	Zip-lock	19											
MB200	4-mL-Vial						19						
CP200	petri-slide	19											
F680	250-mL-bottle		12										
F2000	250-mL-bottle		1										
E680	15-mL-falcon							10					
S680-L	MULTIPLATES								10				
E2000	15-mL-falcon							19					
AI	petri-slide	28											
AS	2-mL-cryotube											28	
AF	Zip-lock							28					
SP330	2-mL-cryotube											50	
MP330	2-mL-cryotube							11					
CP330	petri-slide	14											
TOC	30-mL-bottle								2				
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube											2	
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube											2	
S025-L	15-mL-falcon								33				
S520-L	5-mL-falcon							33					
FM5	5-mL-falcon				66								
TOTAL	2,022	225	150	179	94	0	106	288	199	12	311	293	165